

Intersection and Subtraction Trees for Berry-Sethi Algorithm

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ABSTRACT

We define the single operation for giving the output to the new state in Berry-Sethi approach of building deterministic finite automata (DFA).

OUTLINE

The main problem in the Berry-Sethi approach [1] is the conformance of the new state to the states added before during each iteration of the algorithm.

We use the single test application of our method [2] for the equivalence of the states to the regular language they represent.

CONCLUSION

The above method is expensive, however, in static mode it can be more productive.

REFERENCES

1. Berry, Gerard, and Ravi Sethi. "From regular expressions to deterministic automata." *Theoretical computer science* 48 (1986): 117-126.
2. Syzdykov, Mirzakhmet. "Deterministic automata for extended regular expressions." *Open Computer Science* 7.1 (2017): 24-28.